

AN ASSESSMENT ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT IN JESUIT OWNED INSTITUTIONS: A CASE STUDY OF ST IGNATIUS COLLEGE

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to assess the implementation of performance management in Jesuit owned institutions. The following objectives informed the research; to determine the influence of performance management process on staff motivation, and to propose measures to improve performance management in Jesuit owned Learning institutions. This research applied a mixed approach that used a descriptive design. The study employed a non-probability purposive sampling on teachers found at St Ignatius College and management. In-depth interviews were done among, Principal, Vice Principal, Heads of Departments, and the Jesuit Provincial office. Data was generated using structured questionnaire, review of documents and interviews. Document analysis was also used to verify documented information that was needed as supportive evidence in the study. It was then analyzed by means of applying thematic analysis techniques based on emerging themes from the study. The study revealed that implementation of performance had commenced with various gaps requiring management attention. The study further revealed that in many instances, the designing, agreeing and reviewing of performance management had gaps including the failure to provide reasonable feedback on the performance of the employees. Thus supervisors preferring to be more subjective in the process to avoid being questioned and at many instances employing central tendency rating methods. The study recommended the need for schools to ensure that the managers and immediate supervisors are empowered and schools to implement consistency performance bonus awards to deserving employees. The study further recommended the need for management to cascade the strategic objectives to the departments for their extraction of performance objectives.

Keywords: Motivation, Performance management, Strategies, Reviews, Training and development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Performance management is a communication process by which managers and employees work together to plan, monitor and review an employee's work objectives and overall contribution to the organization. More than just an annual performance review, performance management is the continuous process of setting objectives, assessing progress and providing ongoing coaching and feedback to ensure that employees are meeting their objectives and career goals (Masonde and Daka, 2023). There is much more to performance management than the annual performance review meeting. Performance management is a continuous process of planning, coaching and reviewing employee performance.

In the past, educational institutions enjoyed exceptional autonomy, but are nowadays confronted with an explosion of control measures, steering mechanisms and increasing accountability pressures (Bajaj, 2018). These multiple pressures for measurable performance output and outcome have been inspired by the doctrines of the 'New Public Management (NPM)'-paradigm. NPM advocates the adoption of private management instruments within public sector organizations in order to increase efficiency, effectiveness and quality (Osborne and Gaebler, 2013; Pollitt, 2013; Hood, 2011; Bach, 2016; Pollitt and Bouckae, 2013). The development of a performance management system at the individual level supports performance management at the organizational level. Performance management at the organizational level means the implementation of managerial systems such as strategic planning, quality management and balanced scorecards (Sander, 2017). Several multi-dimensional frameworks have been introduced, attempting to incorporate outcome and result-oriented process measures for delivering long-term organizational objectives.

St Ignatius College embarked on the implementation of the strategic plan 2019 to 2023 with the focus of attaining key strategic objectives and formulation of a performance management. The strategic objectives included the following; Attain 100% pass marks in 2019 to 2023, Achieve 70% and 80% at both senior and junior classes, meet 40% and 50% distinction rates in senior and junior classes respectively, increase enrolment rates from 220-pupil population in 2019 to 580 in 2023. Apparently, the need for performance management system have been introduced at public sector that includes the teaching council of Zambia, and at permanent secretariat level in all government ministries. St Ignatius College introduced a long term strategic objectives of implementing long term strategic objectives which includes the formulation and implementation of performance management and development process and similarly, higher education institutions have commenced the various performance management practices in their organization for various motivations.

St. Ignatius College began its journey as a Jesuit secondary school in 1976, but its legacy as one of the oldest private secondary schools in Zambia. In 1976, Leopards Hill Secondary School arose out of a genuine and practical need resulting from a mid-70s government announcement that an estimated 100,000 students had failed to secure a grade eight place and would therefore be unable to proceed with further studies. Leopards Hill was a community school project aimed at not only providing educational space for students but also providing assistance to the government. By June 1980, the first students were enrolled with the belief that these students would in turn go out and serve their communities and by extension, the nation. The motto of this school was and will continue to be "learning for service of God and others". Over the years, the school has not only played a significant role in providing spiritual, academic, and character formation to its students but it has also been responding to the developing needs of the community as a whole. Therefore, the need of the College was and still remain to raise young leaders who are intellectually competent not only through the value systems of the College but also the academic performance of the College as a whole. The need to formulate and implement performance management and development process was a holistic approach of ensuring the attainment of strategic objectives and achievement of excellent results.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

It is declared by Morrison (2010) and Masonde and Daka (2023) that performance management and development process is a powerful tool of managing the performance of the employees in any given institution and evaluating employee contributions or value additions over time and a tool to identifying performance gaps. In view of this Morrison (2010) states that performance management and development process can help an institution to realign the performance outcomes of an employee to the required strategic objectives as outlined in strategic plan forecasting attainments over time. Unlike the Knowledge of performance implementation as outlined by Morrison (2010), there hasn't been any assessment of evaluation of performance management tool at St Ignatius College to determine performance outcomes as per the strategic plan 2019 to 2023. It is against this background of wanting to see increased performance of learners to the desired levels at St Ignatius College that the school commenced the implementation of performance management and development process. Hence, the need to conduct the study on the assessment of performance management and development process and its outcome on achievement of desired student performance, motivation levels of staff, the period of times the reviews are conducted.

1.2 Research Objectives

1. To determine the influence of performance management on staff motivation at St Ignatius College.
2. To propose measures to improve performance management at St Ignatius College.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

The study was informed by the Balanced Scorecard Framework. The balanced scorecard framework (Kaplan and Norton, 1996) is one framework for performance management process that is often utilized by organization. A balanced score card is a selected set of measures that provides a balanced and timely view of business performance specific to an area of responsibility” (Chang and Morgan, 2000, P.8). When organizations adopt a strategic scorecard, the intent is to create excitement and commitment, communicate a shared vision, stretch aspiration and risk taking, and provide every employee with a scorecard. Chang and Morgan (2000) introduces the concept of ‘cascading’ where the goals and strategic objectives of the organizations cascade down through the various organizational levels or departments to the members of the departments identifying their contributions to the success of the departments which entails the success of the entire organization. Cascading ends with individual balanced scorecards that are linked to the original strategic plans of the organizations. A balanced scorecard is a strategic management performance metric it has helped companies identify and improve their internal operations to help their external outcomes (Masonde and Daka, 2023). It will help St Ignatius College measures past performance data and provides organizations with feedback on how to make better decisions in the future.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Performance Management and Evaluation Process

The performance management process can be regarded as an administrative tool for planning and controlling the assignment of work and how well or poorly it is completed. It is used to assist in delegating the carrying out of work and control the conduct of the work so that the planned results are obtained (Jabłoński, 2017). Therefore, Performance management system is an ongoing process which facilitates continuous monitoring and evaluation of the employees’ performance against the predetermined targets thereby enhancing organization effectiveness (Armstrong, 2009). And due to the declining service and poor academic performance of the students an effective performance management system aligned to organizational objectives can lead to improved individual, agency and public sector performance as a whole (Australian Public Service Commission, 2013).

In the performance management process, the employees and their immediate supervisors must sit informally and review employees past and present performances and set future directions or objectives. Performance management is the basis of assessing the three key elements of performance management namely: contribution made for the period, competencies demonstrated and continuous developmental areas. Such meetings are the means through which the primary performance management elements of measurements like feedback, positive reinforcement, exchange of views and agreement could be accomplished.

2.2. Effects of performance management and development on staff motivation

The relationship between performance management and employee motivation is currently undergoing radical changes, as new emerging technologies combine with the impact of the coronavirus pandemic to create a new reality. Performance management that focuses on employee wellbeing as much as it does on achieving goals is paving the way for greater levels of motivation and quality of employee output.

Akey (2014) embarked on a study on school performance management on teacher performance with respect to the correlation of teacher performance and student performance in community secondary schools in Tanzania. The study adopted a descriptive case study design. The findings revealed that, teacher performance was not effective means of determining the performance of the students as the basis of student performance had other factors such as heredity, socialization, family background and the environment in which a child was raised among many other factors. On the other hand, the study proposed the holistic implementation of performance management in order to take into consideration continuous counselling of the student, parental meetings with the school authorities and exposure of the students to various realities of life to attain the desired goal of performance management process. St Ignatius College has deliberately formulated policies to achieve academic achievements and the parents were oriented to the process and these processes are not optional but mandatory for all parents that aspire for admission in Jesuit school. Therefore, stakeholder participation is proving to be key component to the implementation of performance management process. The specialized program of learner support program to reinforce areas of learning gaps in student to leverage the efforts of the teaching staff and strategic support staff in the process as the outcome of student results has clearly shown as the reflection of teacher input. As a result

of performance management process, behavioral attributes of the teaching staff have drastically changed and initiative was now the order of the day as some teaching staff would opt to work over the weekend to complete syllabi coverage and attain excellent results.

Under other conditions, Patton (2015) directed a study on Jesuit schools in island. The study aimed to explore whether parents' participation, school culture and value system, corporate image and introduction of performance management process had an impact on the performance of the both the teaching staff and the students. The study employed mixed research method using interview, questions, documentary review and focus group discussion. The study reviewed that teachers and management viewed that a strong learning cultures and parent's participation was a major contributing factor to the excellent attainment of academic student outcomes, to date, schools in island are not implementing performance management and development process yet their academic performance was as their expectations every financial year. The schools considered value imperative approaches to be important in improving teacher performance and student performance outcomes.

However, teachers and management were not happy with the fact that most of the time; school management did not bother to provide feedback on their children performance so as to keep track of their performance consistently. The recommendations put forward included changing behavior and attitudes of the student to their learning process, consistent guidance and counselling sessions or talks, developing a strong value imperative brand that could sustain performance of the students and a deeper approach to holistic learning. Therefore, if performance management was to have an impact and influence academic outcomes, the school authorities need to put in place measures to performance of students and their academic outcomes. One of the questions that this research seeks to respond to is: whether the introduction of performance management has a significant impact on the performance of the students in Jesuit schools in Zambia.

In a different study Babu and Kumari (2013) investigated the influence of various practices or factors of student performance towards performance management process. The study examined the provision of result outcome feedback to parents in improving teacher and student performance in secondary schools in Western Uganda. The study concluded that despite the value attached to academic performance of the students in the theoretical and policy debates towards the improvement of teacher performance, many school management of authority lacked the required leadership acumen of providing required strategic support to the operationalized staff.

Graume (2017) piloted a study on the influence of performance management system on student performance division of the Ministry of Education in secondary schools in Adamawa State of Nigeria. The findings show that principals, teachers and parents significantly differed in their views on the impact of performance management implemented in the schools in relation to the outcomes of student performance. However, they both agreed on stakeholder participation in the process of transmitting knowledge to the students. The study recommended among others that school authorities to adopt a communication process that would achieve flow of adequate information at all times on the learning process of the students. Therefore, performance management and development were to holistically incorporate the academic progress of the students. Nevertheless, this research aimed at establishing the implementation of performance management and development process in Jesuit schools in Zambia.

2.3 Measures to improve performance management

Clark (2012) carried out in Research addressing the effects of school climate and culture in measuring the performance of the students. The purpose of this study was to comprehensively examine school culture and climate in relation to performance management systems and the effects of culture and climate to student performance. The results of an online survey administered to 159 participants revealed that the school culture and climate had a significant impact on employee performance and student performance outcomes. On the other hand, Coca, & Easton, (2007). Conducted a study on supervisor employee relations using a purposive sampling technique of 120 participants and in his finding, Zhang, and Yin (2011) and Silwamba and Daka (2021) state that developing positive relations between the supervisor and the employee was one of the techniques for designing a positive culture and climate that foster productive in a work environment. To this effect, St Ignatius College developed a deliberate wellness program that allows for continued climate and culture in the College and the results of the research would endeavor to find out its impact on the performance of the staff and the students in their performance outcomes.

In another study, Goe, Bell, & Little (2008) predicted employees' perceived effectiveness of their performance management through consistent employee engagement. The process of employee engagement was found to be the strongest predictor of perceived effectiveness and employee performance. Furthermore, Routman (2012) and Lungu and Daka (2022) in their studies identified performance management system that were significant to measure the performance of employees. The results suggested that organizations should implement these characteristics into their performance management system to increase perceived effectiveness of the system and employee engagement. St Ignatius College had incorporated these suggestions and criteria and their impact or influence to performance management process were measured and analyzed in this study.

The study by Gabriel et al., (2011), was a longitudinal survey. This particular study used a combination of a cross section survey and phenomenology. The study found that consistent communication in managing performance management process was key to attain the desired strategic objectives and one measure of improving performance management. The factors that Gabriel (2011) and Chizyuka and Daka (2021) identified as key measures to improving performance of employees and students were commendable but nothing was said about stakeholder involvement in the implementation of performance management. It was not clear if the school had made a consideration of incorporate other stakeholders as a measure of the impact of the performance management system. The knowledge gap regarding the inclusion of stakeholder as a measure to improving performance will be addressed in this research as the delegate of education of the Jesuit southern Africa province was identified as a key informant to this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study used a mixed approach. In conducting the study, the research aimed to identify how people describe their own experiences and the meaning they attribute to their experiences. Therefore, the research was conducted in the participant's natural environment, which ensured that in depth and factual data was collected through questionnaires and interviews. Apart from that, qualitative approach allowed the researchers to ask broader questions through interviews. Creswell (2012) asserts that qualitative studies depend on the views of the participants and involves analyzing of data for description and themes using text analysis and interpreting the larger meaning of the findings. A descriptive design was employed as the study involved collecting data to explore and describe how St Ignatius College implements its policy on performance management and development process. Babcock (2011) posits that the purpose of descriptive research design is to describe, analyze, and interpret patterns, systems, processes of individuals and groups and draw out inferences that are helpful to address the identified problem directly or guide other people's investigations. Dash (2015) also points out that descriptive designs attempt to analyses, interpret, ascertain and report on the current status of interaction that exist between individuals and groups or area. Consequently, a descriptive design helped the researcher to interpret the status of the phenomena under study to interpret the findings after the administration of a questionnaire and interviews with key informants to the study.

This study comprised the Principal, Vice Principal, and Heads of Departments, teaching staff, support staff and representatives from the Jesuit office of the southern Africa province. These were believed to play a key role in the implementation of performance management and development process. In addition, the targeted group were viewed as being critical to the process because the Jesuit office is charged with the responsible of ensuring the Jesuit tradition is upheld in the process of implementing Ignatian values.

The study will use non-probability purposive sampling on teachers found at St Ignatius College and management. In-depth interviews will be done among, Principal, Vice Principal, Heads of Departments, and the Jesuit Provincial office. However, sampling of teachers, supporting staff was done using purposive sampling, homogeneous type to be specifics. Homogeneous sampling is a purposive sampling technique that aims to achieve a homogeneous sample; that is, a sample whose units (people, cases, etc.) share the same (or very similar) characteristics or traits (example, a group of people that are similar in terms of age, gender, background, occupation).

A study comprised thirty - three (33) participants; among them were the principal, vice principal, representative from the society of Jesuits, five heads of departments, twelve support staff and thirteen teaching staff. All the participants who were included in the sample had a key role in the implementation of performance management. Coding of management position was done to ensure differentiation and confidentiality among the participants so that their personal identity is not discovered (Fisher, 2013). For easy identification of the participating management positions, codes were assigned to management positions as follows: School Principal (SP -1), School Vice Principal (SVP-2), Head of Languages Department (HLD -3),

Head of Natural Science department (HNSD-4), Head Mathematics and Computers (HMC-5), Head Maintenance department (HMD -6) and Jesuit Representative from the office of the southern Africa Province (JRSAP- 7).

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

Data were analysed using the objectives of the study. The first objective was on the influence of performance management on staff motivation.

4.1 Influence of Performance Management on Staff Motivation.

Figure 4.1: Influence of Performance Management on Staff Motivation.

Source: Field data, 2023

From the objective relating to influence of performance management to staff motivation, a figure above show that only of 3 employees agreed, 8 totally agreed, while 12 disagreed and 10 totally disagreed. This percentage terms demonstrates that 9 % of the employees agreed, 24 % totally agreed, while 36 % disagreed and 31 % totally disagreed.

The following are some of the sentiments that different participants mentioned in responding to their views on the influence of performance management system.

Participant (SP-1) had this to say:

The current performance management system does not represent the aspirations of an education service sectors and was fit for banking sector in achieving sales ratios and not for a teaching institution.

School vice Principal (SVP-2)

The current performance system has negatively been received by the teaching staff citing probably the objectives was to give reasons for dismissing teachers if the students fail their examinations, if management was to assure the teachers to the contrary that the performance system meant well, then the system can be said to be okay for us to implement.

The participant (HLD-3) indicated that:

For us in languages department and particularly me the Head of Department, paper work has increased on top of my job description of marking student scripts for homework, comprehension, composition, assessment papers plus now the performance of the teaching staff.

The participant (HNS-4) indicated that:

For me as Head natural science, the current performance is more appealing for administrative positions because they did not design lesson plan and teaching files for purposes of monitoring their teaching process, it is time consuming and unnecessary.

Participant (HMD-6) had this to say:

On the current performance management system, for us in maintenance we just ask to be taught these new things because we don't know but willing to learn.

4.2 Measures to Improve Performance Management at St Ignatius College.

The second objective targeted at understanding from the participants what they considered as measures at improving the performance management process aimed at improving academic performance of learners at St Ignatius College. From the interviews conducted, the respondents had the following sentiments responding to the strategies of improving performance management in the implementation of strategies at St Ignatius College.

Participant (SP-1) had this to say:

My response to the Question would be that, the school needed to do much in sensitizing the employees to fully appreciate the concept of performance management and clearly the implementation is okay though the education sector is probably implementing this for the first time including our school and ideally our policy guidance is three times in a given financial year.

School vice Principal (SVP-2)

was of the view that, the competencies levels of the teaching staff were extremely low because of lack of interest from the teaching staff to implement the process, in that teachers were used to the process of schemes of work, lesson planning and therefore, being asked to implement the process of performance management was viewed by the teaching staff as a share of wasted time.

The participant (HLD-3) indicated that:

As a school, when introducing new concepts, ideas or processes and requesting employees to implement the said programs, employees should be subjected to training and development so as to mitigate the resistance to change that may be experienced by the School. Therefore, the implementation process was purely subjective and conducted only once in a financial year.

The participant (HNS-4) indicated that:

In as much as the introduction of performance management was welcome to measure performance, the process was being implemented in a hurry and one wonders to the rush was for. The process needed to be systematic at the level of the employees and gradually develop them to appreciate the concepts and ensure appreciation of the policy currently the frequency of performance so far had been conducted once from the time I commenced my tenure of employment.

Participant (HMC -5) had this to say:

I have no doubt that we have competent staff both in the department and the entire school, the approach to implementing the process had not taken into consideration the teaching production time, the competencies and performance of the teaching positions are measured using results and not any other tool. However, the department has only implemented performance management twice due to time constraints.

Participant (HMD-6) had this to say:

What I can say is that for my maintenance staff, we know nothing about performance management because our role is to sweep, clean and make sure the surrounding is looking clean. In addition, It was discovered that some employees did not have well defined job descriptions while it could further be observed from the study that majority of the employees had well defined job descriptions as one of the tools to designing performance management contracts.

From the majority point of view, the study discovered that this was consistent to performance management principles and a strong foundation to the implementation process. To achieve its ultimate purpose, the study found out that the employer should explain the job description of the employees in writing and this was equally inline to the new employment code number 3, 2019 which requires an employer to explain to the employees their job descriptions and avoid role conflict and gain commitment from both parties.

Participant (JRSAP-7) had this to say

It would be difficult to state the competencies levels of staff though it would be important to state that the Board had tasked management to allocate adequate resources to the financial budget as a strategic support to achieve the implementation of this desired process.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 Influence of performance management.

As indicated by objective one, the study sought to determine the influence of performance management and development process on staff motivation. The study revealed that the introduction of performance management process did not have an influence on staff motivation because the strategic plan had projected unrealistic targets. The targets could not be attained due to student development stages being different. This is in agreement with the study by Akey (2014) who demonstrated that the development stages of children has a great impact on their academic performance. The findings also showed that the introduction of performance management was to be of influence if a reward system was put in place for academic staff. These finding were in line also with a study by Patton (2015) and Chizyuka and Daka (2021) who found out that if management of organization use a workable performance reward system in learning institutions, then academic staff can be motivated to work harder. In the case of Ignatius College, the school had incorporated an awarding system that recognized employee recognition and performance adjustment was one of the key strategic objectives. Furthermore, a study by Chiwoya and Daka (2022) on job satisfaction between those in public schools and those in private schools demonstrated the need for an effective reward system to maintain staff high performance. This works well as also stated in the study by Lungu and Daka (2021) on internal monitoring and evaluation in secondary schools where the findings showed that if performance was linked to strategic objectives, then academic performance of learners increased.

5.2 Measures to Improve Performance Management at St Ignatius College.

Armstrong (2010) argues that if the primary objective of the performance management process is to identify and resolve performance gaps, executing it in an acceptable manner can yield acceptable results. From the findings, stakeholders had different views as discussed in this document and could help St Ignatius College improve its performance management processes.

5.2.1. Performance Feedback

The findings revealed that the majority of staff were not informed or given feedback after performance review process was conducted. This is conflicting with the performance management principles which states that giving employee's feedback is vital for improvement of performance (Segal, 2017; Silwamba and Daka, 2021). The best performance reviews are a two-way discussion and focus on the employer assessing the performance of an employee and setting goals for improvement. The implication of the findings are that employees would not know why they were being rated either poorly or rated as being met or exceeded a particular performance target which can cause anxiety and dissatisfaction and affects performance review processes effectiveness. Management should demand that supervisors submit detailed report indicating employee's areas of improvement including performance management audits.

5.2.2 Challenge of Employee competencies

The findings reviewed that supervisors struggled to understand the performance management process and that some members of staff did not have the interest to learn. This could be attributed to the differences between the duties of the job and the role profiling. The findings are inconsistent with Krgent (2017), who states that if a role profile does not address some key features of the job or that what the jobholder does was not updated regularly to address the expansion of duties. This can confuse employees and cause them to loss focus. In this study, the heads of departments and support staff struggled with the performance management implementation processes. The Administrative and Accounts staff were slightly more

comfortable with the performance management process, which the supervisors attributed to their duties especially administrative staff.

In addition, the findings further reviewed that such processes were not applicable to an education service sector but would be more suitable in banks and other and marketing departments. The findings are inconsistent with Obisis (2017), who stated that often the same review form set is applied to a larger but not identical set of employees. For a performance management process to be effective an organization should not therefore design the tool as one size fits all because the more complicated jobs were, the more complicated a performance management process would be. It would be of help to adjust the tool to a school set up.

5.2.3. Training and Development

The findings reviewed that the initial training of staff on performance management process at the commencement of its implementation was not adequate and that the College did not have enough resources to adequately cover all the areas and ensure that development process was embedded in the College structures effectively. In addition, the supervisors were of the strongest view that there was little or no training provided from the reviewers. The process of reviewing performance does not just happen and organizations should not assume that the supervisors know what they are doing or ought to do. According to Luneburg (2016), it is important that training was provided to introduce supervisors to the philosophy of performance management and development process at the organization level. This statement was supported by a survey conducted by Aberdeen Group (2014), which demonstrated that of the 50% of firms that did not give managers any training in performance management process had challenges in implementing it. Furthermore, the supervisors interviewed were of the view that the performance management process was not compatible with the organizational culture. It was difficult to rate their subordinates poorly in view of the college value of exhibiting compassion as an Ignatian value. Instead, they balanced the results by giving average ratings thereby compromising the objectivity and effectiveness of performance management process. These findings were consistent with Deblieux (2013) who explained that if a halo effect is used, supervisors rating of the subordinate does not depend on the actual performance but on the other dimensions. In such cases, the subordinates are rated consistently high or medium on all performance reviews.

5.2.4 Performance aligned to Strategic Objectives

From the supervisors interviewed, their responses were that the school had a laid procedure of extracting organizational objectives from the strategic plan and was well articulated by the leadership team of the school. They explained that most supervisors concentrate on the performance management process as outlined by the strategic plan and as designed from the action plan for the year. The findings are consistent with Obisis (2017), who stated that the performance management process would be much more effective if it focused on the dynamics of the business in relation to the changes in the business environment. Performance management effectiveness was attributed be achieved if the objectives are properly aligned with the organization strategic plan and corporate action plans which aligns individual performance contracts.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Performance management and development process has proven to be a challenge for Jesuit owned institutions in their quest to improve organizational performance. This was compounded by the increasing call for private schools to be more accountable in their operations. Therefore, performance management and development process should not be an end in itself but a means to effective organizational performance. In other words, the performance management should provide the ability to reveal the performance gaps and means of resolving them. As such, an effective and suitable performance management process in an organization should be to provide necessary performance feedback to employees and should be the basis for supervisor's action.

The main objective of this study was to analyses performance and development process effectiveness in Jesuit owned institutions using St Ignatius College as a sample. The focus was determined whether its implementation was an active tool for measuring performance in Jesuit schools.

The study made the following recommendations:

- i) St Ignatius College should ensure training of leadership and management positions for effective execution of the function's tasks and responsibilities of performance management and development process.

- ii) St Ignatius College should design and circulate the performance implementation tools so that subordinates were well aware of the review dates for their implementation process.
- iii) Managers and heads of departments should ensure that the performance management and development contracts were linked to the overall strategic objectives as outlined in the strategic plan.
- iv) St Ignatius College should consider designing performance contracts to suit the various categories of employees in their Implementation.

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